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Cotton Cultivation in the Context of Agricultural Digitalization: A Case Study of Uzbekistan

KEYWORDS

cotton cultivation,
digitalisation of agriculture,
cotton growing in Uzbekistan,
modern precision farming technologies,
innovative water management systems

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Cotton remains a strategic export commodity and one of the most significant agricultural crops: the Republic of Uzbekistan annually produces approximately 3 million tonnes of seed cotton and extracts about 1–1.1 million tonnes of cotton fibre, thereby facilitating the transition towards a fully integrated value-added production chain. In this context, the implementation of the Agricultural Development Strategy for 2020–2030, which envisages the large-scale application of scientific advances and “smart” technologies, is of particular relevance. However, within the local context, the actual effectiveness, economic viability, and socio-economic consequences of adopting these innovations, as well as their impact on the cotton sector’s value chain, remain insufficiently explored. *The aim of this study* is to systematically examine the relevance of digitalisation in cotton cultivation in Uzbekistan and to assess its influence on crop productivity, economic performance, and the sustainability of water resources.

Materials and Methods. The materials used included peer-reviewed journal articles, analytical reports, news and online resources, as well as governmental and other databases. The research methods employed comprised an analytical review and synthesis of secondary sources, tabular classification and content analysis of digital technologies, a comparative analysis of technologies based on predefined criteria, and a description of the components and architecture of digital agronomic systems.

Results. Digital solutions for cotton production are presented, encompassing modern precision agriculture technologies and innovative water management systems. Subject to appropriate financial investment and infrastructural support, these approaches are capable of reducing operational expenditures, increasing profitability, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the sector. The key technical components include precision seeding technologies, robotisation, and solar-powered irrigation, which enhance agronomic efficiency and resource conservation. Furthermore, real-time monitoring and satellite-based data facilitate operational soil moisture management and more precise irrigation scheduling.

Conclusion. The implementation of digital technologies and artificial intelligence significantly improves the efficiency of agricultural process management in cotton cultivation and contributes to the sector’s resilience in the context of climate change and accelerating technological progress.

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INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan plays a pivotal role in national employment and food security. It contributes approximately 19.4% of the gross domestic product (GDP) and provides more than 3.3 million jobs, a figure that significantly exceeds the share of other economic sectors. Simultaneously, climate change poses substantial challenges to the sustainability of this sector. Research indicates that rising temperatures and increased aridity may lead to reduced yields of major agricultural crops, including wheat, cotton, rice, and maize [1; 2]. Furthermore, temperature increases cause shifts in growing seasons, thereby creating difficulties for traditional agronomic practices and field work planning.

Approximately half of the land area of the Republic of Uzbekistan is classified as agricultural land. Of particular importance are irrigated lands, which constitute arable areas totaling approximately 3,988.5 thousand hectares; these lands account for about 95% of total agricultural output. The primary sources of fresh water for irrigation are the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers, whose water resources are declining due to climate change and increasing water consumption in neighboring countries [3].

According to estimates by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), approximately 100 million family farming households across 80 countries depend directly on cotton cultivation and the cotton industry. Cotton plays an essential role in the economies of many low-income and developing countries. Overall, the global value of cotton production is estimated at approximately USD 50 billion, while the volume of international trade in this commodity amounts to about USD 20 billion [4].

Each year, Uzbekistan produces approximately 3 million tonnes of seed cotton, from which about 1–1.1 million tonnes of cotton fibre are extracted, rendering the country one of the world's largest producers of this valuable raw material. In recent years, large-scale reforms have been actively implemented, with the objective of transitioning from simple cotton exports to the development of a full production chain characterized by high added value – from yarn production to finished clothing. Cotton, as one of the most important agricultural crops, has served as the principal source of foreign exchange earnings for the country [5].

The implementation of tasks aimed at increasing the efficiency of agricultural production is carried out within the framework of the Agricultural Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030, approved by Presidential

Decree. The fulfillment of this Strategy largely requires the widespread adoption of scientific achievements and an increase in the level of agricultural culture. To achieve this goal, the application and introduction of “smart” technologies are also necessary [6].

Digital technologies (drones, drip irrigation, precision farming) play a key role in the modernization of cotton cultivation in Uzbekistan, increasing yields by 30–40% and reducing losses caused by pests [7].

The main directions include smart irrigation (drip irrigation) [8], the use of drones for field monitoring [9], GPS navigation of agricultural machinery, and automated crop recording [10], all of which are necessary due to ongoing climatic changes. In Uzbekistan, it is planned to accelerate the development of local cotton varieties, expand the use of agricultural drones, and introduce digital technologies into the agricultural sector [11].

This study is aimed at analyzing the impact of agricultural digitalization on the efficiency of cotton cultivation in Uzbekistan. The key objectives are as follows:

- to identify the most important digital solutions in cotton growing;
- to examine the most successful practices in the implementation of digital technologies in cotton cultivation;
- to analyze the most successful practices in the implementation of digital technologies in cotton cultivation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials for this study included articles from peer-reviewed scientific journals, namely: the Journal of Soils and Plant Nutrients, the Journal of Cotton Research, Agroforestry Systems, Irrigation Science, Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy, the Russian Journal of Plant Physiology, the European Journal of Science, Innovation and Technology, Agronomy for Sustainable Development, among others. In addition, the following were used: an analytical report on the assessment of opportunities for the implementation of climate-resilient solutions in the agricultural sector (UNDP); news reports, official websites and online resources (FAO Newsroom, AA.com.tr, YuzNews, Rudesignshop.ru, Podrobno.uz, Kursiv Media Uzbekistan, Gazeta.uz, Brecorder, Google Arts & Culture, etc.); the government website gov.uz; and the WIPO Green database of digital agronomic tools.

The research methods employed consisted of an analytical review and synthesis of secondary sources, tabular classification and content analysis of digital technologies, a comparative analysis of technologies according to established criteria, a financial-economic plan or investment and replication assessment, and a description of system components and architecture.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, a number of methods are utilized as the principal approaches in traditional cotton cultivation: agronomic methods, the application of fertilizers and pesticides, agronomic irrigation management, mechanical soil tillage, pest and disease control using biological and chemical agents, among others.

G. Mgendi examines the field of precision agriculture, with particular attention to its tangible benefits, challenges, and future developmental directions. A detailed understanding of the impact of precision agriculture on crop production, animal husbandry, economic indicators, and environmental sustainability is provided by the scholar. Key issues, such as data security and implementation costs, are identified, while innovative solutions and promising advances in this field are also highlighted [12].

M. Pandit studied the attitudes of cotton producers toward the adoption of precision agriculture technologies. A total of 474 events were recorded by the author, with an average of 0.70 events per farming enterprise [13].

K. Paudelshna found that younger and more educated cotton producers rapidly adopted precision agriculture technologies as soon as these technologies became available. Furthermore, farm size and farm income positively influence the likelihood of technology adoption by cotton growers [14].

W. Ma with co-authors argue that effective nitrogen fertilizer application is critical for optimizing cotton yield and nitrogen use efficiency, particularly in drip irrigation systems where precise nutrient management is essential. The researchers' results demonstrate that the application of 60 kg N ha⁻¹ of ammonium sulfate as a starter fertilizer effectively increases cotton yield [15].

S. Deng with co-authors found that intercropping cotton with cumin, which has a shorter growth period, proved to be an effective strategy for improving land use efficiency during the early growth stages of cotton. According to the authors, growing cumin in mixed stands at medium density improved cotton biomass accumulation

characteristics and increased resource use efficiency (land and water) as well as economic benefits, due to a stronger compensation effect following cumin harvest under subsurface drip irrigation without mulching [16].

M. Negash with co-authors propose a transition to a sustainable, solar-powered, circular economy for cotton production. A regenerative agroforestry system based on cotton cultivation is proposed by the scholars, which takes into account the management of light, water, soil, and tree canopy. This cotton production system is capable of improving soil health, reducing chemical inputs, increasing biodiversity, enhancing the quality and quantity of available water, augmenting carbon sequestration, and improving the living conditions of local communities [17].

G. Yi with co-authors contend that the irrigation of cotton with magnetized brackish water can be widely applied in arid regions due to the scarcity of fresh water, without any reduction in yield. According to the authors, irrigation with magnetized water significantly reduced root zone salinization and increased cotton yield, thereby demonstrating that proper timing of magnetized brackish water irrigation optimizes soil desalination, productivity, and water use efficiency in saline agricultural lands [18].

T. W. Griffin with co-authors indicate that real-world applications of distributed ledger technology to current data management issues on cotton farms include: (1) ensuring the quality of yield monitoring data; (2) tracking sustainability indicators and resources related to cotton fibre quality from the cotton gin down to sub-field levels; and (3) enhancing supply chain coordination by providing additional information to warehouse managers [19].

Cotton cultivation in different countries is characterized by specific features that depend on the level of digitalization. In countries with low levels of digital integration (e.g., India, Pakistan, African countries), manual methods and traditional technologies are predominantly employed. Countries with high levels of digitalization (e.g., the United States, Australia, Israel) apply automation, drones, sensors, and big data analytics.

S. Alidou with co-authors believe that the widespread availability of mobile communications and the Internet constitutes an important factor driving digitalization in the agricultural sector of Africa. According to the authors, the level of banking services, labor utilization, cotton area under cultivation, and knowledge of agricultural information and exchange platforms significantly influenced the use

of digital devices in agriculture. However, the use of more advanced technologies, such as drones and sensors, has not yet become a reality for these producers [20].

V. Mendes and E. Viola present an institutional analysis of “Agriculture 4.0” in Brazil, focusing on the challenges and opportunities that this new paradigm opens up for the country's environmental governance architecture. According to the authors, the adoption of “Agriculture 4.0” in the country is slow but gradual. Digital agriculture remains far from a reality for the majority of Brazilian family farms, especially those located in the northern and northeastern regions [21].

S. Lakshmanan with co-authors write that mechanized cotton harvesting (High-Density Planting System, HDPS) in India is intended to address labor shortages and rising production costs. The application of plant growth regulators (PGRs) is also necessary to control leaf canopy architecture. According to the scholars, the integration of HDPS and PGR application leads to optimal plant architecture for improving mechanized harvesting efficiency [22].

S. Manibharathi with co-authors indicate that the adoption of high-density planting systems is gaining popularity in India to increase cotton yield. This system is also suitable for mechanized harvesting, which reduces labor costs, increases resource use efficiency, ensures timely harvesting, preserves cotton quality, and potentially enhances productivity and profitability [23].

R. Patil with co-authors conducted a comprehensive literature review on various types of pests affecting cotton crops both globally and specifically in India. Deep learning models were also employed by the researchers for disease detection in cotton plants [24].

S. Ashraf with co-authors report that the average cotton yield in Pakistan remains at 570.99 kg/ha, while its production incurs higher costs than all other crops. Yield in Pakistan is below its potential, profitability is sharply declining, and farmers are abandoning cotton in favor of alternative summer season crops. Six factors affecting cotton yield were identified by the scholars: (i) climate change; (ii) varietal issues; (iii) pesticide use; (iv) perception of institutional services; (v) farmer attitudes; and (vi) soil and environmental health [25].

S. Mahmood indicates that cotton growing in Pakistan faces numerous challenges, including climate change, water scarcity, declining soil fertility, and pest infestations. According to the scholar, techniques such as spectral imaging and satellite imagery can provide insight into cotton crop health, alerting farmers to pest infestations or water shortages in real time. Furthermore, Internet of Things (IoT) devices can

continuously monitor soil temperature, moisture, and water levels, all of which are crucial for cotton crop health [26].

H. Sareban with co-authors examined the problems of cotton production in arid regions of Iran by determining optimal irrigation strategies, planting density, and nutrient management. According to the researchers, a combination of biological and chemical fertilizers demonstrated a synergistic effect on nutrient uptake and utilization under water deficit conditions [27].

X. Liu with co-authors note that chemical plant growth regulation using plant growth regulators represents a key strategy for achieving high efficiency in cotton production in China. The researchers examine the application of mepiquat chloride at three evolutionary levels: (1) symptom-based corrective application; (2) systematic programming of growth stages; and (3) integrated management with agronomic practices [28].

F. Sultana with co-authors evaluated the yield, biomass accumulation, and growth of nine cotton genotypes in Henan Province (China) over three growing seasons (2017–2019) under different climatic conditions. According to the researchers, based on correlation analysis, temperature and precipitation had a negative effect on raw cotton production and final biomass, whereas climatic parameters showed a favorable correlation with the harvest index [29].

G. Kassa with co-authors note that in Northern Australia, interest in expanding cotton production has grown in recent years; however, production faces significant challenges, including infertile soils, harsh climatic conditions, and substantial environmental trade-offs. The scholars demonstrate that cotton production in tropical regions is constrained by extreme and unpredictable climatic conditions, biodiversity risks, high carbon and water footprints, significant production costs, and health hazards for producers and agricultural workers related to pesticide use [30].

Many Australian cotton growers now employ advanced water measurement technology to determine when to irrigate their crops using fully automated systems. Water data are collected in the field using sensors, which transmit this information to a decision-support tool that calculates whether the plant requires water. The irrigation system is then activated depending on the crop's real-time needs. This type of technology has helped the Australian cotton industry increase water use efficiency by more than 40% over the past 15 years [31].

In the context of the development of digital technologies in agriculture, new cotton cultivation methods are being introduced that significantly increase

production efficiency and sustainability. Key directions include: precision agriculture based on the use of sensors, satellite data and GPS technologies for precise fertilization and irrigation; drones and unmanned aerial vehicles; big data analytics; mobile platforms, etc.

P. A. Nicholson and R. Pearson write that cotton is a critically important commodity for the global economy and one of the leading high-value agricultural crops. The search for methods to apply data-driven artificial intelligence technologies to ensure the viability of this industry is of global importance [32].

S. Aksoy with co-authors believe that Agroengineering 5.0 represents a major step forward in agricultural development, combining advanced technologies with intelligent engineering solutions to create more efficient and sustainable farming practices. In order to unlock its full potential, issues such as cost, access to technology, and farmer training still need to be addressed [33].

Bal, S. et al. write that advances in artificial intelligence and digital technologies are opening up revolutionary opportunities to improve pest monitoring, forecasting, and management. Ethical considerations, including data ownership, equity, and accessibility, remain central to ensuring that AI-driven pest management benefits both smallholder farms and technologically advanced farms [34].

G. Sarwar with co-authors write that, under current climate change conditions, the challenges of cotton growing can be mitigated through digital innovations and their application. The introduction of technologies such as smart sensors, satellite imagery, management software/machine learning, and autonomous machinery can transform crop management decision-making, thereby providing higher yields and reduced resource costs [35].

T. N. Ete with co-authors write that diseases caused by various pathogens, such as bacterial blight, leaf curl, and Fusarium wilt, constitute a major problem for cotton crops. It is important to identify the type of disease before it spreads, classify it, and apply appropriate measures to increase cotton yield. ResNet-50 has been effectively used to classify these cotton diseases. This is a convolutional neural network (CNN) developed in 2015 by a Microsoft Research team [36].

According to S. Alidou with co-authors, the majority of producers have adopted digital technologies; however, many do not hold a positive perception of them. A significant proportion of cotton producers (63.69%) expressed no opinion regarding the security level of digital platforms, and this trend persisted regardless of gender, age, education level, and land area cultivated. Small-scale farmers

(less than 5 hectares) predominated over other producers in terms of positive evaluations related to the usefulness of digitalization and the Internet, as well as the strengthening of social ties [37].

Thus, research underlines that the development and adoption of digital technologies and artificial intelligence play a pivotal role in ensuring the sustainability, efficiency, and adaptability of cotton cultivation in the context of climate change and technological progress. Leading international scholars note that the use of advanced solutions such as smart sensors, satellite imagery, automated machinery, and data analytics can significantly increase yields, reduce costs, and manage pests and diseases. However, to fully unlock the potential of these technologies, issues of cost, access, and farmer training need to be addressed.

RESULTS

Digital agriculture

The utilization of digital technologies in the agricultural sector significantly enhances the efficiency of agricultural process management. Precision farming systems, drones, satellite monitoring, soil moisture sensors, and automated irrigation systems enable cost optimization, yield improvement, and minimization of environmental impact. Digital platforms and big data analytics assist farmers in making informed decisions, predicting yields, and responding promptly to changes in weather conditions. The introduction of such technologies contributes to sustainable agricultural development, loss reduction, and increased farm profitability.

Example

The “Merganteks” cluster in the Olot district of the Bukhara region has successfully implemented modern agricultural technologies. On the fields of farmer Shukurullo Urunov, early-maturing Chinese cotton varieties with an expected yield of 50 centners per hectare were sown following grain crops. Drip irrigation is applied for watering, and drones are employed to monitor crop conditions and field maintenance. This experience combines traditional and modern technologies, thereby demonstrating the successful adaptation of foreign varieties to local conditions and the enhancement of agricultural productivity [38].

Satellite monitoring

Satellite monitoring is an advanced technology for observing agricultural land using data obtained from satellites. This system makes it possible to obtain up-to-

date information on soil condition, crop growth, moisture levels, temperature, and other key parameters affecting yield.

Satellites regularly capture images of the Earth's surface in various spectral ranges, which facilitates the identification of changes in soil structure, the determination of plant health, and even the prediction of potential threats such as droughts, diseases, or pests. The analysis of these data allows farmers to respond quickly to changes in fields, thereby optimizing the use of fertilizers, water, and plant protection products.

One of the main advantages of satellite monitoring is its ability to cover large areas, rendering it an indispensable tool for agricultural management at the national and regional levels. When combined with other digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence and big data, satellite monitoring contributes to making the agricultural sector more sustainable, productive, and environmentally friendly.

In particular, a project initiated by the Global Textile Group envisages the application of precision farming principles through satellite monitoring to optimize cotton cultivation on an area of 12,341 hectares in the Fergana region of Uzbekistan. As part of a collaboration with EOS Data Analytics (EOSDA) and local agricultural producers, the project aims to increase cotton yields, improve field monitoring efficiency, and ensure sustainable cotton cultivation in accordance with Better Cotton Initiative (BCI) standards. The EOSDA crop monitoring system employed provides real-time data on crop conditions, including growth dynamics, soil nutrient levels, and potential problems such as pest infestation. These data enable prompt and targeted management decisions, which has led to a 75–80% increase in cotton yields over three years and has allowed Global Textile to construct three new factories [39].

Big Data and artificial intelligence

Big data and artificial intelligence in agriculture are technologies that are fundamentally transforming the approach to farming, making it more precise, efficient, and sustainable. Big data encompasses vast arrays of information originating from various sources: satellite imagery, field sensors, weather forecasts, soil data, yield histories, and even market trends. These data are analyzed using powerful algorithms, revealing hidden patterns and providing farmers with valuable insights for decision-making.

Artificial intelligence (AI) complements big data by automatically processing and interpreting information. Machine learning assists in predicting yields, detecting plant diseases at early stages, and optimizing irrigation and fertilization. For example,

AI algorithms can analyze satellite imagery and predict drought or diseases long before they are noticed by humans.

Through these technologies, farmers are enabled to significantly reduce costs, minimize yield losses, and alleviate the environmental burden by utilizing resources rationally. The introduction of big data and artificial intelligence renders agriculture not only more productive but also adaptive to climate change and economic challenges.

In 2025, Agrobank allocated 1.6 trillion soums (approximately USD 131.6 million) for the purchase of agricultural machinery. By 2026, it is planned to increase the volume of financing to 3.9 trillion soums (approximately USD 321 million). In addition, the bank intends to launch pilot projects on the introduction of artificial intelligence in the livestock, horticulture, and water management sectors [40].

The main modern precision farming technologies and innovative water management systems are listed below (see Table 1).

Table 1

Digital solutions for cotton cultivation

Solution	Description	Developer	Country
Precision crop planting	The 20 20 program (monitor) is an advanced real-time monitoring and control system for seeding processes. It provides precise control over seeding rate, depth, seed placement quality, and fertilizer application, allowing farmers to promptly adjust settings for maximum productivity.	Precision Planting	USA
Robotic precision agriculture technologies	A robotic device for optimizing herbicide and fertilizer application.	SwarmFarm Robotics	Australia
Low-pressure irrigation technology	A low-pressure drip irrigation system. Includes low-flow drip units and a connector system that facilitates easy water collection.	Netafim	Israel
Irrigation management systems	The technology allows farmers to determine irrigation schedules based on local or remote access via mobile phone or the Internet. It consists of a network of sensors, pumps, and control valves for remote monitoring and irrigation management.	Agua Control	Chile
Solar-powered autonomous irrigation	A water pumping system powered by solar panels, combined with an efficient drip irrigation system. Suitable for farms of approximately one hectare; requires a set of cables, batteries, panels, and pumps.	SunCulture	Kenya
Real-time water supply system monitoring	Smart sensors transmit data to a web platform for online monitoring and analysis.	SmartHydro	Chile

Solar-powered mini-desalination units	A solar-powered mini-desalination unit for water treatment in rural areas. Capacity: 5.3–40.0 thousand liters/day. Technology: reverse osmosis.	Elemental Water Makers	Netherlands
Irrigation monitoring and control using satellite data	Real-time satellite data acquisition for assessing the condition of agricultural land.	Satellogic	USA

Note: Compiled based on the analytical report on the comprehensive assessment of business opportunities and the potential for the implementation of climate-resilient solutions.

Subject to adequate financial investment and infrastructural support, these solutions are capable of reducing operating costs, increasing the profitability of the cotton business, and creating conditions for long-term sustainability.

Precision seeding technologies and robotization improve agronomic performance and reduce the overconsumption of seeds and resources. Solar-powered irrigation reduces water and energy costs. Real-time monitoring and satellite data provide operational moisture management, loss prevention, and more accurate irrigation planning.

Specific Digital Solutions for Cotton Cultivation

Particular attention is merited by Wahaless Smart Farming, which represents an agro-ecological management system for controlling and assessing water and energy consumption, as well as for remote monitoring of soil condition using smartphones and IoT sensors.

Key findings are as follows:

- Wahaless Smart Farming connects digital infrastructure and agro-ecological methodology for real-time management of water and energy flows and soil monitoring.
- Three complementary components – tele-irrigation, the Hussa method, and the integrated ecological digital farm – form a holistic framework focused on emission reduction, data transparency, and farm autonomy.
- The system is intended for global application in arid regions and supports the transition to sustainable agricultural technologies through standardized protocols for data collection, carbon balance calculation, and production process monitoring [41].

The TrueCause Above software, developed by Aker, serves as a tool for unmanned systems, providing operational detection of weeds, diseases, and stress factors during the agricultural season, thereby optimizing agronomic treatments.

TrueCause Stand Count provides an assessment of yield potential after emergence and generates replanting recommendations, thereby facilitating more accurate correction of planting actions in the early stages of cultivation.

Aker soil maps enable the instant formation of soil zones with targeted sampling points, supporting the development of sowing and fertilization recommendations based on local soil characteristics.

The proposed tools demonstrate the applied nature of digital agronomy: they expand farmers' capabilities, stimulate the development of sustainable agriculture, and exert a positive influence on crop management decision-making, ultimately benefiting both the agricultural sector and the environment [42].

One of Materra's leading innovations is its proprietary AI-based agronomy tool. This tool provides year-round farmer support, making it possible to cultivate different cotton varieties using digital AI tools. Materra's materials also provide verifiable data on the environmental impact of each cotton bale, compliant with regulatory requirements, thereby ensuring unprecedented transparency and trust across the entire supply chain in the fashion industry. Materra's concept is being realized through a pilot industrial farm currently operating in Gujarat, India [43].

GrowSphere OS is a digital agricultural platform designed for precise irrigation and fertigation. It combines field controllers, sensors, cloud services, and mobile access into a single, user-friendly interface, allowing farmers to efficiently plan, control, and adjust irrigation schedules. The system provides real-time field condition visibility, remote valve control, and automatic notifications of operational problems. The dashboard supports online and offline modes, with the possibility of automation while retaining manual control. GrowSphere assists in preventing over-irrigation or under-irrigation, reducing water and fertilizer consumption, and lowering energy use. Users can create irrigation protocols, receive data-driven recommendations, and generate reports to ensure yield traceability and product quality control [44].

Dymax is a platform for collecting geospatial data from satellites, radar, aerial data, and drones, combining it with real-time Internet of Things information. It then constructs a structured database that enables valuable analytical insights to be extracted and new patterns to be identified. Applications include crop monitoring,

assessment of sown areas, identification of illegal mining, tracking of deforestation, detection of land encroachment, and other tasks [45].

A set of digital tools for monitoring is listed below (see Table 2).

Table 2

Digital tools

Product	IOT-S300AQ	Waspnote Plug and Sense! Smart Agriculture Xtreme	Decagon EM50 Data Logger	Vantage Pro2 Plus	VTU / Voltage Tracking Unit
Sensor Type	Air quality	Temperature, Humidity, Atmospheric pressure, Solar radiation, UV radiation, Shortwave radiation, Soil moisture	Temperature, Humidity, Atmospheric pressure, Soil moisture	Temperature, Humidity, Wind speed, Precipitation, Solar radiation, UV radiation	Energy monitoring
Communication Protocol	Modbus RTU, RS-485	LoRaWAN, Zigbee, Modbus RTU, RS-485	GSM/GPRS	Zigbee	Modbus RTU, RS-485
Power Source	Mains electricity	Battery-powered, Solar-powered	Battery-powered, Solar-powered	Battery-powered, Solar-powered	Mains electricity

For monitoring climate and agronomic conditions in the field, the following are suitable: Waspnote, Waspnote Plug and Sense! Xtreme, and Vantage Pro2 Plus (when mobility and cloud capabilities are required). The EM50 can be used as a reliable data logger for long-term field measurements. For air quality monitoring, the IOT-S300AQ in combination with an RS-485 gateway is recommended. For energy accounting and power supply control in industrial environments, a VTU based on Modbus RTU in conjunction with another controller or SCADA system is appropriate.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present results indicate that the development and widespread adoption of digital technologies and artificial intelligence play a pivotal role in ensuring the sustainability, efficiency, and adaptability of cotton cultivation in the context of climate change and accelerating technological progress. According

to leading international scholars, the application of advanced solutions – intelligent sensors, satellite imagery, automated machinery, and advanced data analytics – can lead to significant yield increases, cost reductions, and more effective pest and disease management.

Y. Li with co-authors provide a preliminary insight into promising technologies that may play a more significant role in sustainable intensification in the future, taking into account the challenges of market transfer and on-farm adoption, as well as being complemented by non-technological innovations in farm management and institutional support [46]. However, to fully unlock the potential of these technologies, solutions are required to reduce costs, ensure access, and improve farmer qualifications; in particular, the development of accessible infrastructure, personnel training, and the creation of sustainable business models are needed.

The present results demonstrate that the introduction of digital technologies and artificial intelligence significantly increases the efficiency of agricultural process management in cotton cultivation and contributes to its sustainability in the context of a changing climate and accelerating technological progress. According to leading international scholars, the application of advanced solutions – intelligent sensors, satellite monitoring, robotic machinery, and advanced data analytics – can lead to significant yield increases, cost reductions, and more effective pest and disease management. However, to fully unlock the potential of these technologies, measures to reduce costs, ensure access, and expand farmer education and training are necessary. The section presented specific digital solutions for cotton, including modern precision farming technologies and innovative water management systems. With adequate funding and infrastructure support, these approaches are capable of reducing operating costs, increasing profitability, and creating conditions for the long-term sustainability of the sector. Precision seeding technologies, robotization, and solar-powered irrigation enhance agronomic efficiency and conserve resources; real-time monitoring and satellite data provide operational moisture management and more accurate irrigation planning.

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